

O Alto Ribatejo Revisitado

www.cph.ipt.pt

N. 0 // Dezembro 2013 // Instituto Politécnico de Tomar

PROPRIETÁRIO

Centro de Pré-História, Instituto Politécnico de Tomar
Edifício M - Campus da Quinta do Contador, Estrada da Serra, 2300-313 Tomar
NIPC 503 767 549

DIRETORA

Ana Cruz, Centro de Pré-História

SUB-DIRETORA

Ana Graça, Centro de Pré-História

DESIGN GRÁFICO

Gabinete de Comunicação e Imagem
Instituto Politécnico de Tomar

EDIÇÃO

Centro de Pré-História

ISSN

2183-1386

PERIODICIDADE

Anual

SEDE DE REDACÇÃO

Centro de Pré-História

CONSELHO DE REDACÇÃO

Professora Doutora Primitiva Bueno Ramirez, Universidad de Alcalá de Henares
Professor Doutor Rodrigo Balbín Behrmann, Universidad de Alcalá de Henares
Doutor Enrique Cerrillo-Cuenca, Instituto de Arqueología de Mérida – CSIC – Governo de Extremadura
Doutor António Gonzalez Cordero, IES Zurbarán de Navalmoral de la Mata (Cáceres)

ANOTADA NA ERC

Índice

EDITORIAL.....	7
O SÍTIO ARQUEOLÓGICO ANTA I DO REGO DA MURTA.....	9
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO	
APLICAÇÕES INFORMÁTICAS À PRÉ-HISTÓRIA – CASO TOMAR.....	18
ANTÓNIO CASIMIRO TEIXEIRA BAPTISTA	
VESTÍGIOS ARQUEOLÓGICOS NA FREGUESIA DE RIO DE MOINHOS – ABRANTES	29
ÁLVARO BATISTA	
O SÍTIO ARQUEOLÓGICO PRÉ-HISTÓRICO DA FARROEIRA (ALVAIÁZERE): RESULTADOS DE UMA INTERVENÇÃO NÃO INTRUSIVA.	52
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO	
LAPA COMPRIDA DO CASTELEJO – ESTUDO LABORATORIAL DOS RESTOS ÓSSEOS HUMANOS EXUMADOS DE UMA GRUTA-NECRÓPOLE (ALVADOS – PORTO DE MÓS).....	59
TIAGO TOMÉ	
LAPA RASTEIRA DO CASTELEJO (ALVADOS, PORTO DE MÓS) – RELATÓRIO DO ESTUDO LABORATORIAL DOS RESTOS ÓSSEOS HUMANOS EXUMADOS NA CAMPANHA DE ESCAVAÇÃO DE OUTUBRO DE 2009	81
TIAGO TOMÉ	
DADOS ARQUEOLÓGICOS INÉDITOS A NORTE DO CONCELHO DE ABRANTES.....	97
ÁLVARO BATISTA E FILOMENA GASPAR	
LAPA RASTEIRA DO CASTELEJO (ALVADOS, PORTO DE MÓS) – RELATÓRIO DO ESTUDO DO ESPÓLIO OSTEOLÓGICO HUMANO EXUMADO NAS CAMPANHAS DE 2009 E 2010	117
TIAGO TOMÉ	
APLICAÇÕES INFORMÁTICAS À ARQUEOLOGIA. OS EXEMPLOS DA GRUTA DO CADAVAL E DA ANTA 1 DE VAL DA LAJE (TOMAR, PORTUGAL)	133
ANA CRUZ	
ESCAVAÇÃO DO CASTELO VELHO DA ZIMBREIRA (2011)	154
DAVIDE DELFINO	
IDENTIFYING MIGRANTS IN THE LATE NEOLITHIC BURIALS OF THE ANTAS OF REGO DA MURTA (ALVAIÁZERE, PORTUGAL) USING STRONTIUM ISOTOPES	190
ANNA J. WATERMAN, ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO, JONATHAN T. THOMAS & DAVID W. PEATE	
CONTRIBUTO PARA A ANÁLISE DO MEGALITISMO NO ALTO RIBATEJO (1998-2001)	198
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO	

OS MENIRES DO COMPLEXO MEGALÍTICO DE REGO DA MURTA (ALVAIÁZERE, LEIRIA): RESULTADOS DAS INTERVENÇÕES DO MENIR I E II DE REGO DA MURTA.	213
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO	
A PRE-HISTORIC ART DATABASE AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH A GIS EXPERIMENT	226
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO	
ANÁLISIS NO DESTRUCTIVO DE LA MATERIA COLORANTE MEDIANTE INSTRUMENTACIÓN RAMAN PORTÁTIL EN EL ARTE PARIETAL DE LA CUEVA DE LA PEÑA (SAN ROMÁN DE CANDAMO, ASTURIAS)245	
M. OLIVARES, X. MURELAGAB, K. CASTROA, D. GARATEC Y M.S. CORCHÓN	
THE UNDERWATER HERITAGE OF SANTA CATARINA ISLAND (PRAIA DOS INGLESES), BRAZIL: A DIGITAL PEDAGOGICAL GAME	254
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO, CLÁUDIO MONTEIRO, ALEXANDRE VIANA, MARCELO MOURA E FRANCISCO NOELLI	
GROTA SA OMU 'E TZIU GIOVANNI MURGIA: INTERVENTO ARCHEOLOGICO	263
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO, GIUSI GRADOLI, ROSALBA FLORES E CLÁUDIO MONTEIRO	
PROJECTO EBO: ARQUEOLOGIA E PATRIMÓNIO COMO FACTORES DE SUSTENTABILIDADE EDESENVOLVIMENTO LOCAL	303
LUIZ OOSTERBEEK E CRISTINA POMBARES MARTINS	
THE MOMENT PAST PROJECT	315
ALEXANDRA FIGUEIREDO, LUIZ OOSTERBEEK, G. GUIZI, MARTA AZARELLO, S. WESTENGAARD, SARA CURA, G. BURENHULT, A. MINELLI, U. THUNHOHENSTEIN E CARLO PERETTO	
O ESTUDO DA CERÂMICA: UM QUADRO REFERENTE AOS TRÊS GRUPOS INDÍGENAS DO SUL DO BRASIL	337
SAMIR ALEXANDRE ROCHA E MIRIAN BAPTISTA CARLE	

EDITORIAL

Editorial

“Antrope” tem como objectivo oferecer um fórum de investigação, colocado numa óptica interdisciplinar, ao longo do tempo, centrado na História e Arqueologia. Pretendemos contribuir para alicerçar temáticas, que transcendem paradigmas específicos e estanques das várias épocas, nas Ciências Sociais e Humanas e nas Ciências da Terra e da Vida. Desta forma, será proporcionada uma visão mais ampla e completa sobre os processos de evolução ou ruptura das sociedades.

“Antrope” enquanto publicação pretende cumprir todos os requisitos de qualidade estabelecidos para as revistas científicas em formato electrónico, nomeadamente através dos elementos do Conselho de Redacção e dos elementos do Comité de Leitura.

“Antrope” proporciona a divulgação dos seus conteúdos em meio académico, entre especialistas, estudantes e profissionais, funcionando como plataforma entre o meio profissional e o académico, bem como, de ligação, nas temáticas abrangidas, entre a região do Médio Tejo Português, onde se insere, e as outras regiões, quer a nível nacional, quer a nível internacional.

Este número é composto por uma secção uniforme à qual foi dado o título de “O Alto Ribatejo Revisitado” e uma outra, a Sectio, onde se publica informação que está na esfera internacional.

A vertente principal fala-nos dos resultados arqueológicos de trabalhos desenvolvidos nesta região do Médio Tejo Português mais precisamente em Alvaiázere, Mação, Abrantes e Tomar e ainda, o trabalho desenvolvido sobre a base de dados do Centro de Pré-História do Instituto Politécnico de Tomar.

O bloco apelidado de Sectio apresenta versões variadas de outros trabalhos também eles desenvolvidos no âmbito da Arqueologia como os trabalhos implementados em Angola, em Itália, no Brasil, em Espanha e em Portugal.

Com este número 0 pretendemos preencher um espaço que faltava na literatura arqueológica e que, estamos certos, dará os seus frutos a curto prazo.

A informação arqueográfica agora apresentada surge como o facto primário sobre o qual se poderão fazer sínteses no futuro.

Aos leitores e colaboradores caberá dar força a este novo projecto.

Tomar, 2 de Dezembro de 2013

**IDENTIFYING MIGRANTS IN THE LATE NEOLITHIC BURIALS
OF THE ANTAS OF REGO DA MURTA (ALVAIÁZERE,
PORTUGAL) USING STRONTIUM ISOTOPES**

Anna J. Waterman

University of Yowa

Alexandra Figueiredo

Instituto Politécnico de Tomar

Jonathan T. Thomas

University of Yowa

David W. Peate

University of Yowa

Identifying migrants in the Late Neolithic burials of the Antas of Rego da Murta (Alvaiázere, Portugal) using Strontium Isotopes

Anna J. Waterman, Alexandra Figueiredo, Jonathan T. Thomas & David W. Peate

ABSTRACT

This study uses strontium isotope ratios ($87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$) in dental enamel to distinguish migrant individuals from Late Neolithic populations interred at the burial sites of Anta da Rego da Murta I and Anta da Rego da Murta 2 (Alvaiázere, Portugal). Strontium isotopes are absorbed into local plants and incorporated into the hard tissues of animals and humans through water and food intake. The isotopic composition of the bioavailable strontium depends on the local geology and the types of rocks and sediments in the subsurface. As dental enamel is formed during childhood and not subsequently remodeled, its $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ ratio records the geologic signature of one's childhood landscape. By comparing the $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ in the dental enamel of interred individuals with the local range of the burial environment determined from local fauna it is possible to identify individuals who spent at least part of their childhoods in a different location (Price, *et al*, 1994; Price, *et al*, 2002).

Keywords: Archaeology; Megalithism; Strontium isotopes ratios; Alvaiázere; Human Osteology.

RESUMO

Este artigo pretende apresentar um estudo utilizando isótopos de estrôncio ($87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$) no esmalte dental para distinguir indivíduos migrantes de populações neolíticas tardias enterrados nos cemitérios da Anta I de Rego da Murta e Anta II da Rego da Murta (Alvaiázere, Portugal). Isótopos de estrôncio são absorvidos pelas plantas locais e incorporados nos tecidos duros de animais e de seres humanos através da ingestão de água e alimentos. A composição isotópica do estrôncio biodisponível depende da geologia local e os tipos de rochas e sedimentos no subsolo. Como o esmalte dental é formado durante a infância e não posteriormente remodelada, a sua relação $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ registra a assinatura geológica de uma paisagem de infância. Ao comparar a $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ no esmalte dentário de indivíduos enterrados com o intervalo do meio ambiente local, determinado a partir da fauna locais, é possível identificar os indivíduos que passaram, pelo menos, parte da sua infância num local diferente (Price, *et al*, 1994; Price, *et al*, 2002).

Palavras-chave: Arqueologia; Megalitismo; Isótopos de estrôncio; Alvaiázere; Vestígios osteológicos.

1. SITES

Anta da Rego da Murta I and II are part of the Rego da Murta Late Neolithic/Copper Age megalithic complex located in the Ribatejo region of Portugal near the municipality of Alvaiázere. This complex consists of more than a dozen monuments, including four dolmens (antas). In the area around this complex, several late prehistoric settlements have been identified. In the natural caves surrounding the complex, Late Neolithic/Copper Age burials have also been discovered in which the types of grave goods and the treatment of the human remains are very similar to the ones observed at the megalithic burial monuments. However, in the dolmens, it is more common to find objects of personal adornment manufactured from exotic raw materials, suggesting that some of the individuals in these burials may have been migrants or associated with long distance trade. Other megalithic complexes, like the Rego da Murta complex, have not been found in the region surrounding Alvaiázere, however isolated dolmens, usually ones that have been previously disturbed or destroyed, have been noted (Figueiredo, 2006).

2. MATERIALS

For the site of Anta da Rego da Murta I enamel was sampled from 10 adults (Table 1). For Anta da Rego da Murta II enamel was sampled from 11 adults, 3 adolescents and 1 child (Table 2). Bone or enamel samples were taken from the remains of 8 animals recovered from the burial sites as well in order to establish local baseline $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ ratios. These faunal samples included 3 rodents, 2 rabbits, a horse, a cow and a pig.

Site	Sample	Age estimate	Individual
Rego da Murta I	RMI 110	Adult	Adult 1
Rego da Murta I	RMI 299	Adult	Adult 2
Rego da Murta I	RMI 26	Adult	Adult 3
Rego da Murta I	RM1 279	Adult	Adult 4
Rego da Murta I	RM1 267	Adult	Adult 5
Rego da Murta I	RM1 405	Adult	Adult 6
Rego da Murta I	RM1 674	Adult	Adult 7
Rego da Murta I	RM1 384	Adult	Adult 8
Rego da Murta I	RM1 325	Adult	Adult 9
Rego da Murta I	RM1 305	Adult	Adult 10

Table 1: Samples taken from Rego da Murta I.

Site	Sample	Age estimate	Individual
Rego da Murta II	RM2 163	Young adult	Adult 1

Rego da Murta II	RM2 1000	Young adult	Adult 2
Rego da Murta II	RM2 823	Adult	Adult 3
Rego da Murta II	RM2 802	Adult	Adult 4
Rego da Murta II	RM2 631	Adult	Adult 5
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1003	Adult	Adult 6
Rego da Murta II	RMII 668	Adult	Adult 7
Rego da Murta II	RM2 624	Adult	Adult 8
Rego da Murta II	RM2 5	Adult	Adult 9
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1005	Adult	Adult 10
Rego da Murta II	RM2 807	Adult	Adult 11
Rego da Murta II	RM2 685	10-15 yr	Adol 1
Rego da Murta II	RM2 690	10-15 yr	Adol 2
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1001	10-20 yr	Adol 3
Rego da Murta II	RM2 640	6-9 yr	Child 1

Table 2: Samples taken from Rego da Murta II.

3. METHODS

Enamel surfaces were cleaned with acetone and the top layer of enamel was removed. Next a small amount of enamel (4-10 mg) was removed with a Dremel drill for analysis. Third molars were preferentially selected as the crowns generally form between the ages of seven and sixteen and therefore represent a post weaning time period stretching into adolescence. When not available, 2nd and 1st molars were used instead. Strontium was extracted from acid-digested enamel samples using Sr spec ion-exchange resins in the University of Iowa Department of Geoscience clean lab. $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios were measured using a Nu Plasma HR multicollector inductively-coupled-plasma mass-spectrometer (MC-ICP-MS) in the Department of Geology at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. All ratios were normalized to a NISB 987 international standard value of 0.710268 which had a reproducibility of ± 0.000034 (2 s.d., $n = 46$). The local bioavailable Sr composition is defined by 2 standard deviations from the mean of the small fauna's (rabbit and rodent) $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios for the 10 sampled humans from Rego da Murta I were fairly heterogenous with a high of 0.719810 and a low of 0.711012. The average for the human samples from this burial was 0.713867 ± 0.0032 (Table 3). For Rego da Murta II the $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratio data for the 15 sampled humans were similarly variable with a high of 0.717985, a low of 0.710757, and an average of 0.713491 ± 0.0020 (Table 4). The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ ratios for the sampled

fauna were more homogenous than the sampled humans at either burial site with a high of 0.713955 a low of 0.711062 and an average of 0.712378 ± 0.001019 (Table 5).

For the Rego da Murta burials, the sampled microfauna (rodents and rabbits) were used to define the local $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ ratio range. For the microfauna, the $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ ratios clustered very closely together with a high of 0.712423 a low of 0.711062 an average of 0.711723 ± 0.000502 . Using the standard practice of estimating local range as 2sd from the average of the sampled small fauna, the local range for the Rego da Murta burials is defined as 0.71272 - 0.71071 (Table 6).

Site	Sample	Age estimate	Individual	Sr	Sr corr	
Rego da Murta I	110	RMI	Adult 1	3	0.713935	0.7139159
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	299	RMI	Adult 2	1	0.719688	0.7196509
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	279	RMI 26	Adult 3	8	0.711931	0.7118946
		RM1				
Rego da Murta I	267	RM1	Adult 4	2	0.711608	0.7115710
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	405	RM1	Adult 5	3	0.713670	0.7136331
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	674	RM1	Adult 6	0	0.712522	0.7124848
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	384	RM1	Adult 7	8	0.711649	0.7116126
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	325	RM1	Adult 8	1	0.711050	0.7110129
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	305	RM1	Adult 9	7	0.713125	0.7130885
		Adult				
Rego da Murta I	305	RM1	Adult 10	1	0.719848	0.7198109
		Adult				
				ave	0.7138675	
				sd	0.003227	

Table 3: Results – Rego da Murta I. Migrants in green. Humans that fall just outside of the fauna local ratio range in yellow.

Site	Sample	Age estimate	Individual	Sr	Sr corr
Rego da Murta II	RM2 163	young adult	Adult 1	0.7164659	0.7164287
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1000	young adult	Adult 2	0.7117497	0.7117125
Rego da Murta II	RM2 823	adult	Adult 3	0.7134327	0.7133955
Rego da Murta II	RM2 802	adult	Adult 4	0.7120697	0.7120325
Rego da Murta II	RM2 631	adult	Adult 5	0.7159651	0.7159279
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1003	adult	Adult 6	0.7121590	0.7121218
Rego da Murta II	RMII 668	adult	adult 7	0.7141416	0.7141044
Rego da Murta II	RM2 624	adult	Adult 8	0.7180224	0.7179852
Rego da Murta II	RM2 5	adult	Adult 9	0.7123815	0.7123443
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1005	adult	Adult 10	0.7107951	0.7107579

Rego da Murta II	RM2 807	adult	Adult 11	0.7152145	0.7151773
Rego da Murta II	RM2 685	10-15 yr	Adol 1	0.7132916	0.7132544
Rego da Murta II	RM2 690	10-15 yr	Adol 2	0.7136308	0.7135936
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1001	10-20 yr	Adol 3	0.7120585	0.7120213
Rego da Murta II	RM2 640	6-9 yr	Child 1	0.7115563	0.7115191
				ave	0.7134918
				sd	0.0020712

Table 4: Results – Rego da Murta II. Migrants in green. Humans that fall just outside of the fauna local ratio range in yellow.

Site	Sample	Age estimate	Individual	Sr	Sr corr
Rego da Murta II	RM2 163	young adult	Adult 1	0.7164659	0.7164287
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1000	young adult	Adult 2	0.7117497	0.7117125
Rego da Murta II	RM2 823	adult	Adult 3	0.7134327	0.7133955
Rego da Murta II	RM2 802	adult	Adult 4	0.7120697	0.7120325
Rego da Murta II	RM2 631	adult	Adult 5	0.7159651	0.7159279
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1003	adult	Adult 6	0.7121590	0.7121218
Rego da Murta II	RMII 668	adult	adult 7	0.7141416	0.7141044
Rego da Murta II	RM2 624	adult	Adult 8	0.7180224	0.7179852
Rego da Murta II	RM2 5	adult	Adult 9	0.7123815	0.7123443
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1005	adult	Adult 10	0.7107951	0.7107579
Rego da Murta II	RM2 807	adult	Adult 11	0.7152145	0.7151773
Rego da Murta II	RM2 685	10-15 yr	Adol 1	0.7132916	0.7132544
Rego da Murta II	RM2 690	10-15 yr	Adol 2	0.7136308	0.7135936
Rego da Murta II	RM2 1001	10-20 yr	Adol 3	0.7120585	0.7120213
Rego da Murta II	RM2 640	6-9 yr	Child 1	0.7115563	0.7115191
				ave	0.7134918
				sd	0.0020712

Table 4: Results, Rego da Murta II. Migrants in green. Humans that fall just outside of the fauna local ratio range in yellow.

Sample	Animal	Sr	Sr corr
RM F2	horse	0.7129479	0.7129107
RM F3	Cow	0.7135797	0.7135425
RM F5	Pig	0.7139925	0.7139553
RM F6	rodent	0.7124607	0.7124235
RM F7	rodent	0.7115183	0.7114811
RM F1	rodent	0.7118380	0.7118008
RM F9	rabbit	0.7118886	0.7118514
RM F10	rabbit	0.7110994	0.7110622
		ave	0.7123785
		sd	0.0010195

Table 5: Faunal results. Animals that fall just outside of the fauna local ratio range in yellow.

Sample	Animal	Sr	Sr corr
--------	--------	----	---------

RM F6	rodent	0.7124607	0.7124235
RM F7	rodent	0.7115183	0.7114811
RM F1	rodent	0.7118380	0.7118008
RM F9	rabbit	0.7118886	0.7118514
RM F10	rabbit	0.7110994	0.7110622
		ave	0.7117238
		sd	0.0005020
		2sd	0.0010041
		range high	0.7127280
		range low	0.7107196

Table 6: Small fauna results and calculated local range.

Figure 1: Scatter plot of results. Original local range in dark yellow. Adjusted local range in light yellow.

The standard deviation for the combined human samples was four times greater than the standard deviation for the rodents and rabbits, suggesting that the human population was occupying more diverse landscapes. Based on the data from the microfauna, 5/10 (50%) of the sampled humans from Rego da Murta I can be classified as migrants and 8/15 (53%) of the Rego da Murta II burial are migrants, as well as two of the sampled fauna. Of these 14 individuals and two animals, 7 humans and the 2 animals have $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ ratios that (at 0.7145 or below) are close to the greater end of the local range as defined by the small fauna. The greater variability of the human $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ isotope data when compared to the small fauna, the clustering of humans in the 0.7145- 0.710 $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ ratio range, and the fact that two of the three larger animals also exhibited $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ ratios slightly higher than the local range, suggests that the sampled small fauna may present too narrow of an $87\text{Sr}/86\text{Sr}$ isotope range to accurately describe the local human populations. The difference could be due to the fact that the rabbits and rodent used in this study may have inhabited too limited of a geologic area to represent the lithographic diversity of this geographic region. To compensate for this finding, in this study the local range has been expanded to 0.7145- 0.710. With this adjustment, 2/10 (20%) of the humans from Rego da Murta I and 4/15 (27%) of the humans at

Rego da Murta II continue to be classified as migrants (Figure 1). All of these individuals have $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratios that exceed the local range, from 0.7151- 0.7198. Recent work by Boaventura et al. (2010) found the local strontium isotope range for the large settlement site of Perdigões in the Alentejo region of Portugal to be from 0.714 -0.718. We know that raw materials from the Alentejo commonly made their way into the Ribatejo and it may be that the non-local individuals from Anta da Rego da Murta 1 and Anta da Rego da Murta 2 came from this region as well. However, because of the geologic diversity of the Ribatejo and the surrounding regions of Portugal more information about $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ isotope ratios in small fauna across the landscapes is needed to clarify these results.

CONCLUSION

In sum, dental enamel was sampled from 25 humans and 8 animals from the burials of Anta da Rego da Murta I and Anta da Rego da Murta II and $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ strontium isotope ratios were obtained in order to identify migrant individuals in these burials. Based upon the resulting data 2/10 (20%) of the humans from Rego da Murta I and 4/15 (27%) of the humans at Rego da Murta II can be classified as having had migrated into the region after childhood. Additional strontium isotope mapping in the region is needed to clarify possible places of origin.

REFERENCES

Boaventura R, Hillier M, Grimes V. 2010. Moving around? Testing mobility with strontium isotopes ($^{86}\text{Sr}/^{87}\text{Sr}$) in the Late Neolithic of South-Central Portugal. . 8th Encontro de Arqueologia do Algarve: A Arqueologia e as outras Ciências, October 21st-23rd. Silves. Portugal.

Figueiredo, 2006. Figueiredo, A. (2006) – Complexo Megalítico de Rego da Murta. Pré-História recente do Alto Ribatejo (IV-II^o milénio a.C.): Problemáticas e Interrogações, publicação de dissertação. Revista ângulo. Centro de Pré-História, Instituto Politécnico de Tomar, Vol. I, Vol.IIa e Vol.IIb.

Price TD, Burton JH, Bentley RA. 2002. The characterization of biologically available strontium isotope ratios for the study of prehistoric migration. *Archaeometry* 44:117-135.

Price TD, Grupe G, Schrotter P. 1994. Reconstruction of migration patterns in the Bell Beaker period by stable strontium isotope analysis. *Applied Geochemistry* 9(4):413-417.

